

H2020-SC5-01-2017

MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.8

Launch of external website

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776467.

DOCUMENT STATUS SHEET

Deliverable Title	Launch of external website	
Brief Description	The external web-site available and on-line	
WP number	6	Communication and exploitation of the MED-GOLD value chain
Lead Beneficiary		
Contributors	ENEA, BSC, GMV	
Creation Date	25/01/2018	
Version Number	1.3	
Version Date	26/02/2018	
Deliverable Due Date	28/02/2018	
Actual Delivery Date	28/02/2018	
Nature of the Deliverable	<i>Websites, patents filling</i>	
Dissemination Level/ Audience	PU	<i>PU - Public PP - Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission services RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services</i>

REVISION HISTORY LOG

Version	Date	Created / Modified by	Pages	Comments
1.0	25/01/2018	ENEA	14	Initial Draft
1.1	14/02/2018	GMV	14	Format and minor changes
1.2	15/02/2018	BSC	14	Format and minor changes
1.3	26/02/2018	ENEA	15	Final version

Disclaimer

The information, documentation, tables and figures in this deliverable are written by the MED-GOLD project consortium under EC grant agreement 776467 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

MED-GOLD

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
1. INTRODUCTION.....	9
2. FIRST VERSION OF THE WEB SITE.....	10
ANNEX A. INVITING FORM.....	13
ANNEX B. PRIVACY STATEMENT.....	14

MED-GOLD

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1: A snapshot of the landing page..... 11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MED-GOLD website (www.med-gold.eu) was launched the week before the kick-off meeting of the project. It has the aim to be the gateway to the engagement of stakeholders and to serve the dissemination of the latest information about the project. It has been conceived as a tool aimed to:

- Share knowledge and further developments of climate services that are of interest for the agricultural sector
- Increasing visibility that will boost the market uptake of project results and the replicability on new potential markets
- Raise awareness and contribute to the SDGs and provide relevant information that serves as input for protocols, policies, legal issues, etc.

The website is expected to evolve in response to the evolving needs and developments of the project. One of the main objectives of MED-GOLD is to investigate decision-making processes in the agricultural sector and devise innovative solutions for climate-related threats. To pave the way to attain these objectives, the first version of the website is providing a landing page with a short form for an initial interaction with the MED-GOLD community, defined as the (potential) users from the three MED-GOLD targeted sectors (grapes, olives and durum wheat).

In the course of the project, the website will be periodically updated with information and products based on the project's results, such as news, dissemination materials or information about interesting events and activities related to the project.

The project will also be promoted through social media channels (Facebook and Twitter), linking to the project website whenever relevant.

With this deliverable, the project contributes to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean
Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems
Grant Agreement n° 776467

1. INTRODUCTION

The external website of MED-GOLD (www.med-gold.eu) will be the tool to communicate and disseminate the activities of the project and to engage with stakeholders. It presents general information on the project, project goals, news and events, dissemination materials and project documents. It is also a tool to promote the project and its related activities.

In this perspective, the website was deployed at the very beginning of the project and launched the week before the kick-off meeting. The MED-GOLD website will evolve through a series of new releases that will also help to build the MED-GOLD reputation as long as the project will develop its products. The incremental update of the web-site will be assisted by a specialized company that is being sub-contracted by ENEA to carry out the specific task of providing a professional environment to disseminate the project results with the most updated standards in terms of usability of the information. The website is hosted in start.med-gold.eu, which is the same domain used for the Phabricator, the internal project communication platform, as well as for the forthcoming ICT platform. With the input of other project partners, the website will be periodically updated with information and products based on the project's results.

2. FIRST VERSION OF THE WEB SITE

A launch version of the external website has been created and published on the web. In this way, information of the project can be visible since the very beginning and available during the crucial phase of development of the MED-GOLD community.

One of the main objectives of MED-GOLD is to investigate decision-making processes in the agricultural sector and devise innovative solutions for climate-related threats. The website is therefore constructed in the perspective of facilitating the first steps in this direction.

The first version of the website aims to be a first stop for people who will interact with the project further on, providing the possibility to become part of the MED-GOLD community.

Since most of the project's results have yet to come, a short inviting form for an initial interaction with the MED-GOLD community has been created, which allows visitors to choose their sector of interest (either grape/wine, olive/oil or durum/pasta) before being directed to a simple form for the collection of data. The form is designed to drive potential users to join the MED-GOLD community and provide a space where visitors can share basic contact information that will be used during the prosecution of the project. The forms will continue to be available in future releases of the website.

The short questionnaire contained in the inviting form is reported in ANNEX A. As personal data will be collected, it comes together with a Privacy Statement that is reported in ANNEX B.

English

CLIMATE SERVICE FOR THE MEDITERRANEAN AGRI-FOOD SYSTEM

MED-GOLD is a four-year research and innovation project funded by Horizon 2020, the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, under grant agreement no. 776467.

The [MED-GOLD project](#) will demonstrate the proof-of-concept for climate services in agriculture by developing case studies for three staples of the Mediterranean food system: grape, olive and durum wheat.

Chose your sector of interest

Grape / Wine

Durum / Pasta

Olive oil

[Privacy Statement](#)

Figure 1: A snapshot of the landing page

The initial version of the MED-GOLD website includes different sections:

- Who we are: a partners section where all member institutions of the consortium are shown, with direct links to the home page of each institution.
- Media: material useful for media, such as pictures from the main events (meetings, external conferences, workshops, interview, press releases, etc.) that will be periodically added and updated.
- Contacts section: all the possible ways to connect with MED-GOLD are reported with information about the contact points in the project.

Moreover, the MED-GOLD twitter account ([@medgold_h2020](https://twitter.com/medgold_h2020)) with its associated stream is embedded in the website.

During the lifetime of the project, all these sections will be updated, reorganized and improved following the changing needs of the project. New sections will be added when the definitive version of the website will be produced in the framework of the forthcoming external communication contract.

According to the website analytics, since the web deployment, users have visited the website from about 20 countries, with Italy, Spain, UK, Greece and Portugal in the top five.

All content is made available in the main languages of the project (Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, French) to help further the interaction with local communities of end-users.

ANNEX A. INVITING FORM

MED-GOLD

*Required

Nome/Nombre/Nome/όνομα/Nom/Name *

Your answer

Organização/Azienda/Empresa/εταιρεία/Compagnie/Company

Your answer

Localização/Località/Localidad/Θέση/Emplacement/Place

Your answer

E-mail *

Your answer

A informação climática são úteis para as suas actividades e operações? / Le informazioni sul clima sono utili per la tua attività? / ¿Es la información climática útil para tus actividades/operaciones)? / Είναι χρήσιμες οι πληροφορίες για το κλίμα στις δραστηριότητές σας? / L'information climatique est-elle utile pour vos activités/opérations? / Is climate information helpful to your activities?

Si/Si/Sim/vaí/Oui/Yes

No/No/Não/όχι/Non/no

Forse/Tal vez/Talvez/ίσως/Peut-être/Maybe

SUBMIT Page 1 of 1

Never submit passwords through Google Forms.

ANNEX B. PRIVACY STATEMENT

Collection of data

You can use our website without disclosing your personal data. You are not required to provide personal information as a condition of using our site, except as may be necessary to provide you information at your request. When you use our website, data may be stored for various security purposes. This data may include the name of your Internet service provider, the website that you used to link to our site, the websites that you visit from our site and your IP address. This data could possibly lead to your identification, but we do not use it to do so. We do use the data for statistical purposes, but maintain the anonymity of each individual user so that the person cannot be identified. In cases when personal data is provided to others to provide you products or services you have requested, or for other purposes you have authorized, we rely on technical and organizational means to assure that applicable data security regulations are followed.

Collection and processing of personal data

We collect personal data only when you provide it to us, through registration, completion of forms or e-mails, as part of an order for products or services, inquiries or requests about materials being ordered and similar situations in which you have chosen to provide the information. The database and its contents remain at our company and stay with data processors or servers acting on our behalf and responsible to us. Your personal data will not be passed on by us or by our agents for use by third parties in any form whatsoever, unless we have obtained your consent or are legally required to do so. We will retain control of and responsibility for the use of any personal data you disclose to us. Some of this data may be stored or processed in computers located in other jurisdictions, such as the United States, whose data protection laws may differ from the jurisdiction in which you live. In such cases, we will ensure that appropriate protections are in place to require the data processor in that country to maintain protections on the data that are equivalent to those that apply in the country in which you live.

Purposes of use

The data we collect will only be used for the purpose of supplying you with the requested information or for other purposes for which you have given your consent, except where otherwise provided by law.

Right of access and correction

You have the right to review and amend any personal data stored in our system if you believe it may be out of date or incorrect. Just send an email to med-gold.project@enea.it

Right of cancellation

You have the right at any time to withdraw your consent to the use of your personal data in the future. Again, just send an e-mail to the address: med-gold.project@enea.it

Use of cookies

Cookies are small text files that are stored in the visitor's local browser cache. Using such cookies it is possible to recognize the visitor's browser in order to optimize the website and simplify its use. Data collected via cookies will not be used to determine the personal identity of the website visitor.

END OF DOCUMENT

